

ATTRIBUTES OF LEARNERS' FUNCTIONAL LANGUAGE TEACHING

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***Abstract:** In given article editor tries to clarify the vital components of language teaching on the base of functional approach. She considers the language teaching method, particularly the focused one as an effective ways of achieving advancement of speaking and writing skills of learners aimed to reach fluency in both of them.*

***Key words:** method, teaching, function, oral, written.*

Effective use of additional resources for the development of functional language in the process of teaching English to students, increases their interest and attitude to a foreign language learning. With the help of supplementary educational tools, conducting each lesson in interactive or student centered methods and giving them extra curricula trainings with additional challenging tasks teachers can achieve a noticeable development to reach the desirable progress in this process.

First of all the alphabet of the language and the pronunciation of letters are the primary steps of learners, then the grammar is one of the most important points, the rules related to the tenses is working on in the lesson. It is necessary for the students to memorize new words and according to the level of understanding of the subject and

the level of proficiency. Word memorization is considered to be the most important part of language learning, as well as, phonetically correct pronunciation of words plays not the least important role. Next, listening comprehension is important. The student who listens and understands then starts answering questions. Therefore, first of all, he will start talking in word level etc. striving to connect words separately to combine a sentence with a mere meaning, and in a long term he achieves to join ideas in a number of sentences to succeed in communication.

It should be noted that it is important to use certain methods of innovative technology in the development of functional speech, for example, the use of such types as "brain storming, cluster, zigzag, project, case method" gives a great result.

In some cases, if student cannot speak it judged that if he does not know grammar, so much attention is paid to teaching grammar. But this is a misconception. The level of intellectual capacity, acquisition, perception, understanding and memory is developed differently in each learner. Some receive well by hearing, writing or reading, and others only by seeing and speaking. That is why it is necessary to make effective use of various means of teaching and assimilation, most importantly, methods of developing oral speech, with an individual approach to each student based on his potential. A student who aims to learn a foreign language perfectly should, first of all, master his native language perfectly in all aspects. Below, we will consider some of the innovative educational technologies that are used in practice in teaching a foreign language and have positive results.

The purpose of oral speech training is to prepare students' speech organs to produce remembered words, phrases, to listen and speak English. In particular, oral speech is formed by showing a picture, asking what he sees and who is in the picture, writing a short essay about this situation, expressing his personal position and opinion. If some exercises start with speaking in foreign languages, the students will be in that environment during the lesson. In this process, of course, the ability to listen and understand and speak gradually develops.

The students participating in the training through the "Work in groups" type of modern pedagogy are divided into three groups. Students will be shown an educational film in English that shows the difference between good and bad, hard work and laziness. The first group is given the task of creating questions about this film, the second group is given the task of telling the content of the film, and the third group is given the task of writing an essay about the content of the film. Also, a picture of an event or incident is distributed to the groups. To the members of the group in the same way, that is, "What do you think?" the question is asked. By answering this question, students simultaneously develop the ability to think, speak and express their personal opinion in English, as well as the ability to evaluate and express the situation in different ways.

Using the "Brain storming" method also gives great results and results. In this case, a "brainstorming session" is organized for the students, the initial events of a certain event are read in English, and the students are required to continue it logically. To express thoughts, students should be provided with some required exponents regarding to topic of a lesson. Here are some examples of functions of language as a whole, which are universal for children:

- Instrumental – language used as a means of getting things done (one of the first to be evolved): the “I want” function.

- Regulatory – language used to regulate the behavior of others: the “do as I tell you” function.

- Interactional – use of language in interaction between self and others: the “me and you” function.

- Personal – awareness of language as a form of one’s own identity: the “here I come” function. etc

Of course, during the application of these expressions in oral or inwritten communication, it is appropriate for the teacher to correct every grammatical, lexical, orthographic and other mistakes and shortcomings of the students.

By applying these mixed and pure types of lessons during the training sessions, the development of students' English speaking, listening comprehension, reading, writing, memory and logical thinking is achieved. At the same time, it is possible to improve their level of knowledge and develop intellectual work skills, and to develop the mental, emotional and motivational characteristics of the student.

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